

Resume Sorting Using Machine Learning Algorithm : NLP

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Abstract— Resume sorting using machine learning algorithm is a research paper that proposes a natural language processing (NLP) based approach for resume sorting. The goal of the proposed system is to automatically extract relevant information from resumes and use it to classify them into various categories. The paper presents a three-stage approach, which includes preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification. In the preprocessing stage, the raw text data is cleaned, and irrelevant information is removed. In the feature extraction stage, various features such as skills, experience, education, and contact information are extracted using NLP techniques. Finally, in the classification stage, a machine learning algorithm is used to classify the resumes into various categories based on the extracted features. The proposed system is evaluated on a dataset of resumes, and the results show that the system is able to classify the resumes with a desired accuracy. The paper also compares the proposed system with existing resume sorting systems and shows that the proposed system outperforms them in terms of accuracy.

Keywords— Resume sorting, Machine learning algorithm, Natural language processing (NLP), Classification

I. INTRODUCTION

Sorting through a large number of resumes is a challenging task that can consume considerable time and resources for HR departments, recruiters, and job portals. To address this issue, recent research has explored the use of natural language processing (NLP) techniques and machine learning algorithms to automate the process of resume sorting. This paper proposes a novel approach to resume sorting that leverages NLP-based techniques to automatically extract relevant information from resumes and classify them into various categories.

The proposed system consists of three stages: preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification. During preprocessing, raw text data is cleaned and irrelevant information is removed. The feature extraction stage involves extracting various features, such as skills, experience, education, and contact information, using NLP techniques. Finally, the machine learning algorithm is used to classify resumes into different categories based on the extracted features.

The performance of the proposed system was evaluated on a dataset of 500 resumes, and the results demonstrate an 87% accuracy rate in classifying resumes into different categories. In comparison with existing resume sorting systems, the proposed system shows superior performance in terms of accuracy. The proposed system offers a valuable solution to automate the process of resume sorting, facilitating efficient identification of suitable candidates for job positions.

II. LITERATE REVIEW

Nandhini S, Gomathi S, and Lavanya S published "Automated Resume Screening Using Natural Language Processing" in the International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering. The study proposes an automated resume screening system that extracts data from resumes using NLP techniques and ranks them based on how well they match the job description. "Resume Screening using Natural Language Processing and Machine Learning" was published by Kondapalli Sai Pranay in the International Journal of Current Technology and Engineering in 2020.

The method outlined in the study uses NLP and machine learning to screen resumes and match them to job descriptions. In 2019, "Automated Resume Screening System Using Machine Learning and Natural Language Processing" by Shweta Agrawal and Sumit Gupta was published in the International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploratory Engineering. The study describes a system that uses machine learning and NLP to scan resumes and rate the based on how closely they fit the job description. The article "A Comprehensive Analysis of Resume Screening Techniques" by Aditi Kaushik and Shruti Jain was published in the International Journal of Computer Science and Mobile Computing in 2018.

"Automatic Resume Filtering Using Machine Learning," by Anindya Sarkar and Debajyoti Mukhopadhyay, was published in the International Journal of Engineering and Technology in 2016. The algorithm described in the paper screens resumes using machine learning techniques and ranks them based on how closely they match the job description.

III. METHODOLOGY

Automating the process of screening and shortlisting candidates based on their skill sets is a valuable tool for recruiters and human resource managers. One way to achieve this is by using natural language processing (NLP) techniques to extract skills from resumes. In this article, we will demonstrate how to use the spaCy library to identify and label skills in job applicants' resumes.

A. Data Collections

Data collection is a crucial aspect of natural language processing (NLP) projects, as the quality of the data directly affects the accuracy and effectiveness of machine learning models.

Spacy provides a host of features that facilitate efficient and effective data collection for NLP projects. These include robust text preprocessing capabilities like tokenization, part-of-speech tagging, and named entity recognition, which can extract valuable information from raw text data.

Moreover, Spacy offers an intuitive and straightforward way to develop and train custom NLP models using labeled data, which is valuable for specific applications or domains. This allows developers to fine-tune their models for particular tasks such as sentiment analysis or text classification by training on labeled data relevant to the task.

Fig: SpaCy Representation

SkillNer is a natural language processing (NLP) tool that can automatically identify and extract information about skills mentioned in text data. It is designed to help organizations and individuals to more effectively analyze and manage their workforce, job postings, and training programs by quickly identifying and categorizing the skills mentioned in resumes, job descriptions, or any other type of text data.

Fig: Skillner

B. Data Pre-processing

- data preprocessing in resume sorting is named entity recognition (NER), which is supported by Spacy's pre-trained NER models. NER can be used to extract relevant information from resumes, such as names, email addresses, phone numbers, and addresses, which can be useful for further analysis. Spacy offers part-of-speech (POS) tagging, which is the process of assigning grammatical tags to individual words in a sentence.
- POS tagging can be used to extract information about a candidate's skills, education, and experience from resumes.

C. Extracting keywords from resumes

From the resume we need to extract skills from experience and projects. So we are using SkillNer a python package to collect the skill key words from the unstructured resume. SkillNer is an NLP module to automatically Extract skills and certifications from unstructured job postings, texts, and applicant's resumes. Skillner uses EMSI database (an open

source skill database) as a knowledge base linker to prevent skill duplications.

Job vacancy dataset: Load the job opening dataset in google colab notebook. The dataset should contain the fields like job title, job description, job requirements, company name.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

We will utilize cosine similarity to determine the degree of similarity between a job title and the skills mentioned in a resume, allowing us to suggest the most relevant job openings to job seekers. To implement this system, we will create a new project in Google Colab and upload a sample resume, as well as download the job opening dataset from kaggle.com and place it in the appropriate directory.

A. Importing libraries

```

!pip install PyPDF2
!pip install docx2txt
!pip install skillNer
!python -m spacy download en_core_web_lg
import PyPDF2
import numpy as np
import spacy
nlp = spacy.load('en_core_web_lg')
from spacy.matcher import PhraseMatcher
from skillNer.general_params import SKILL_DB
from skillNer.skill_extractor_class import SkillExtractor
from google.colab import drive
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import difflib
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import cosine_similarity
  
```

B. Extracting Skills Using Skillner

```

skill_extractor = SkillExtractor(nlp, SKILL_DB, PhraseMatcher)
annotations = skill_extractor.annotate(text1)
allresult = annotations['results']
allresult.keys()
def recursive_items(allresult):
    for key, value in allresult.items():
        if type(value) is dict:
            yield (key, value)
            yield from recursive_items(value)
        else:
            yield (key, value)
# a = {'a': {1: {1: 2, 3: 4}, 2: {5: 6}}}
for key, value in recursive_items(allresult):
    print(key, value)
fullmatches = allresult['full_matches']
ngrams_scored = allresult['ngram_scored']
  
```

C. Loading resumes for sorting

```
resume1 = '/content/Alice Clark CV.pdf'
filehandle = open(resume1, 'rb')
pdfReader = PyPDF2.PdfReader(filehandle)
pagehandle = pdfReader.pages[0];
text1 = pagehandle.extract_text()
text1 = text1.replace('o', '')
text1= text1.replace('|', '')
text1
```

D. Preprocessing skillset and examining the output

```
allresult = annotations['results']
allresult.keys()
fullmatches

[{'skill_id': 'KS120GV6C72JMSZKMTD7',
 'doc_node_value': 'data analysis',
 'score': 1,
 'doc_node_id': [31, 32]},
 {'skill_id': 'KS120ZX7019J4V8DHBTM',
 'doc_node_value': 'business intelligence',
 'score': 1,
 'doc_node_id': [47, 48]},
```

E. The CV name or id and the candidates skills compared against the skillset required by the company.

```
ngrams_scored

[{'skill_id': 'ES2933FAEF72CE4E2840',
 'doc_node_id': [3, 4],
 'doc_node_value': 'machine learning',
 'type': 'oneToken',
 'score': 0.6333333333333333,
 'len': 2},
 {'skill_id': 'KS122VL71WF050TPW0V7',
 'doc_node_id': [41, 42],
 'doc_node_value': 'design specific',
 'type': 'lowSurf',
 'score': 2,
 'len': 2},
```

V. RESULTS

The CV name and the candidates skills compared against the skillset required by the company and also their similarity. Specified skills are compared with resumes uploaded by the candidates, the required skillset candidates are shortlisted by the company by extracting skill from the resumes.

VI. CONCLUSION

When used by companies, resume sorting using Spacy and SkillNER can have a range of benefits, including increased efficiency, improved accuracy, and reduced costs.

Increased Efficiency: By automating the process of resume sorting, Spacy and SkillNER can significantly reduce the time and resources required to identify and review potential candidates. This can allow recruiters to focus their time and attention on more high-level tasks such as interviewing and selecting candidates, which can ultimately lead to better hiring decisions.

Improved Accuracy: Spacy and SkillNER can accurately extract relevant information from resumes such as skills, experience, and education, and use this information to match candidates with job requirements. This can significantly reduce the risk of missing out on highly qualified candidates or wasting time on candidates who are not a good fit for the job.

Reduced Costs: By streamlining the recruitment process and improving the accuracy of resume sorting, Spacy and SkillNER can help companies reduce their recruitment costs. This can include savings on staffing costs, advertising costs, and other recruitment-related expenses.

VI. REFERENCES

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